

“Evaluating and Refining Cross-Domain Metadata Exchange Frameworks” - Dagstuhl Workshop, October 13-18, 2024: Summary Report

Overview

The DDI Alliance and CODATA sponsored a workshop titled “[Evaluating and Refining Cross-Domain Metadata Exchange Frameworks](#)” held at Schloss Dagstuhl - Leibniz Center for Informatics in Wadern, Germany from October 13 to October 18, 2024. The main focus of the workshop was on the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF), an output of the recently completed WorldFAIR project. CDIF is a set of guidelines for the coordinated use of standards for describing FAIR resources with a core set of metadata. Development of the guidelines is ongoing, under the

next round of WorldFAIR projects. The workshop was intended to further explore and develop these ideas, for incorporation into CDIF and related efforts.

The event was attended by 24 experts, including participants in the WorldFAIR project and the CDIF Advisory and Working Groups, members of related FAIR initiatives in EOSC, FAIR Impact, and RDA, and potential users from various domains, including hard and social sciences, and representatives of the official statistics community, including the UN Environment Programme and UN groups working on oceans data. The work was organized around topical subgroups, which are described below. The range of outputs was broad, from specific issues with the current set of CDIF recommendations through future directions around data provenance and quality through more exploratory discussions of data context. Overall, the event was a major success – each of the groups was able to meet their goals in terms of substantive outputs, and plans for further work have been established.

Further information can be found at the [workshop wiki](#).

Data Access

This group expanded the current recommendations in CDIF regarding the description of data access conditions in a machine-actionable fashion. This implies the use of the ODRL specification for describing permitted actions. The workshop outlined the full set of interactions needed for granting access to controlled data, and focused on producing examples of specific conditions for data access expressed in ODRL. Multiple use cases were considered.

The worked examples will be incorporated directly into the CDIF guidelines moving forward, and the general analysis will inform further work moving forward.

Data Integration and Mapping

The initial CDIF recommendations focused on the description of how to make data “integration ready” by describing them with DDI-CDI and SKOS/XKOS. This workshop extended that scope to include the description of a full integration process, including not only description of the data but also of semantic artifacts and mappings between these components.

For the work on mappings, the intention is to align with and input to work being undertaken in FAIR Impact and the RDA FAIR Mappings group, with an initial focus on the use of SSSOM. Concrete outputs included a documented, complete example of all aspects of a real-world data integration example taken from the UN Statistical

Division's use case around the SDG Indicators and their disaggregation. Additional use cases were explored, including initial examination of the description in DDI-CDI of data generated by synchrotrons performing X-ray absorption spectroscopy.

Data Discovery, Provenance, and Quality

This group addressed a set of different topics: specific issues/improvements to the existing Discovery profile in CDIF; the overlap between discovery/catalogueing metadata and provenance information; aspects of provenance and quality needed to support search; and the production of SHACL for the current recommendations for using Schema.org, to support validation.

In every case, solid progress was made. Specific wording changes were made to the existing recommendations in several areas, and a major issue regarding the identification of the metadata record, as distinct from the data resource being described, was resolved. The specific metadata needed to provide a PROV instance – based on existing discovery metadata – was identified, along with some extended provenance information for indicating data-generating PROV activities and the source of data derived from other data sets. Further, the use of the Data Quality Vocabulary (DQV) was explored for those cases where quality information might be useful for supporting search.

SHACL rules were also developed for the validation of the existing Discovery profile, following a discussion of what kinds of feedback were appropriate for the validation of this type of a recommendation. In due course, it is intended that all of the relevant profiles would have SHACL validation available to support implementation.

Data Context

This group worked further on a topic which started at the Dagstuhl workshop in 2023. The work is exploratory in nature, looking at the domain-specific models and terminology which need to be made clear in cases of cross-domain sharing when describing the context around data. The focus of this year's group was on understanding how the Observations & Measurements model from the OGC could be understood in the context of cross-domain contextualization of data. The output of the group was a further set of documented examples and a first take on some generic elements of contextual description. In due course, these will be finalized and used as the basis for further metadata profiles in the CDIF recommendations, as appropriate.

Other Outputs

As is often the case in Dagstuhl workshops, unanticipated outputs are produced as a result of discussions during the week. This workshop produced a set of material for producing business-level explanations of CDIF, in short and long forms, for use in communication to management and those unfamiliar with the recommendations and their purpose.

A second important output was a clearer definition of how different metadata profiles would be combined when expressed as JSON-LD, notably as regards the use of DC Terms “conformsTo” to identify which CDIF profiles are being offered, and how the available metadata is structured into graphs to optimize them for use. Also, the need for CDIF to have a domain for the publication of RDF artifacts was identified.

Summary

This workshop included a set of workgroups focused on a range of topics relevant to the further development of the CDIF recommendations and their alignment with related efforts. In each case, solid progress was made. Further, some unexpected outputs were also realized.

At the end of the workshops, participants were encouraged to join the CDIF advisory or working groups, and other plans were made for completing some of the deliverables on a case-by-case basis.

The workshop was broadly successful, contributing in a material way to the further development of CDIF.

The workshop materially supported the DDI Alliance Scientific Work Plan 2024 – 2026: *Goal 2.3 “Proactively engage with and explore possibilities for DDI adoption in cross-domain initiatives and standards, including FAIR and CDIF.”*